

Fase 3: Evaluación pertinencia y relevancia

Los artículos relevantes fueron evaluados mediante los siguientes criterios, lo que permitió finalmente obtener los artículos definidos como primarios:

Categorías y Criterios de Evaluación:

Categoría - Claridad.

Criterios

C1: ¿Es el artículo en sí relevante para el estudio de la ciberseguridad cuántica aplicado a SCF y la IC?

C2: ¿El estudio contribuye con causas, efectos, patrones, métricas o herramientas relevantes?

Categoría- Rigor.

Criterios

R1: ¿Cuál es el objetivo del artículo?

R2: ¿Cuál es la metodología utilizada? ¿Su implementación se adapta a los objetivos de investigación?

R3: ¿Está claro el ambiente de experimentación y puede ser replicado para estudios posteriores?

R4: ¿Se usó una muestra de datos adecuada? ¿La muestra es representativa y suficiente?

Categoría - Relevancia.

Criterios

Re1: ¿Es aplicable el estudio al campo de la ciberseguridad cuántica, especialmente en SCF e IC?

Re2: ¿Se podrá utilizar con trabajos futuros un reto, tendencia, brecha u oportunidad de investigación?

Categoría - Credibilidad.

Criterios

Cr1. ¿Es explícita la discusión del proceso de investigación y la implicación metodológica en el estudio?

Cr2 ¿El resultado alcanzado es claro y entendible?

FUENTE	ID	ARTICULO	AÑO	CITA
Springer	A1	Enhancing Critical Infrastructure Security: Unsupervised Learning Approaches for Anomaly Detection	2024	[1]
Google Académico	A2	AI-Driven Risk Assessment in National Security Projects: Investigating machine learning models to predict and mitigate risks in defense and critical infrastructure	2025	[2]
Google Académico	A3	Cybersecurity risk assessment frameworks for engineering databases: A systematic literature review	2025	[3]
Springer	A4	Generative AI and Cognitive Computing-Driven Intrusion Detection System in Industrial CPS	2024	[9]
Google Académico	A5	Cyber Risk Assessment for Cyber-Physical Systems: A Review of Methodologies and Recommendations for Improved Assessment Effectiveness	2024	[10]
Springer	A6	Deep learning-based authentication for insider threat detection in critical infrastructure	2024	[11]
Springer	A7	Dependency-based security risk assessment for cyber-physical systems	2022	[12]
Google Académico	A8	Construction cybersecurity and critical infrastructure protection: new horizons for Construction 4.0.	2022	[13]
Google Académico	A9	Advances and Strategies in Quantum Computing Integration for Cybersecurity: A Systematic Literature Review	2024	[14]
Google Académico	A10	Exploración de las posibilidades de la computación cuántica para la criptografía	2023	[15]
Google Académico	A11	Exploring AI Security: A Systematic Mapping Study	2025	[16]
Google Académico	A12	An Ontological Model of the Phishing Attack Process		[17]
Google Académico	A13	From Data to Defense: How Ontology Fuels AI in Cyber Threat Detection	2024	[18]
Google Académico	A14	Supply chain cybersecurity: risks, challenges, and strategies for a globalized world	2023	[19]
Google Académico	A15	CVE-LLM: Ontology-Assisted Automatic Vulnerability	2025	[20]

		Evaluation Using Large Language Models		
Google Académico	A16	Driven AI for Automated Data Ontology Classification in Security Architectures	2025	[21]
Google Académico	A17	Enhancing Cybersecurity Situation Awareness Through Knowledge Graphs: An Integrated Survey Including Threats, Vulnerabilities, and Assets	2023	[22]
Google Académico	A18	Detection of Man-in-the-middle (MitM) cyber-attacks in oil and gas process control networks using machine learning algorithms	2023	[23]
Google Académico	A19	Revisión preliminar: ciberseguridad para tecnología de la operación en la era cuántica contra ataques de red a infraestructuras críticas	2024	[24]
Google Académico	A20	Cybersecurity Ontologies: A Systematic Literature Review	2020	[25]
Google Académico	A21	A taxonomy for risk assessment of cyberattacks on critical infrastructure (TRACI)	2023	[26]
Google Académico	A22	A Framework for Conceptual Characterization of Ontologies and its Application in the Cybersecurity Domain	2024	[27]
Google Académico	A23	An Example of of fuzzy ontology usage for risk assessment and attack impact	2024	[28]
Google Académico	A24	A review: Monitoring situational awareness of smart grid cyber-physical systems and critical asset identification	2023	[29]
Google Académico	A25	An integrated approach to cyber risk management with cyber threat intelligence framework to secure critical infrastructure	2024	[30]
Google Académico	A26	Development of a Flexible Information Security Risk Model Using Machine Learning Methods and Ontologies	2024	[31]
Google Académico	A27	Power system resilience and strategies for a sustainable infrastructure: A review	2024	[32]
Google Académico	A28	Predicting cybersecurity threats in critical infrastructure for industry 4.0: a proactive approach based on attacker motivations	2023	[33]
Google Académico	A29	Risk Assessment for Cyber Resilience of Critical Infrastructures: Methods	2024	[34]
Google Académico	A30	CyberBOT: Towards Reliable Cybersecurity Education via Ontology-Grounded Retrieval Augmented Generation	2025	[35]

Google Académico	A31	IRSKG: Unified Intrusion Response System Knowledge Graph Ontology for Cyber Defense	2024	[36]
Google Académico	A32	MoRCiTO: hacia un modelo de referencia de ciberseguridad para la tecnología de la operación como preparación para la era cuántica, a fin de prevenir ataques de red a sistemas ciber-físicos en infraestructuras críticas	2024	[37]
Google Académico	A33	On the Usage of ChatGPT for Integrating CAPEC Attacks into ADVISE Meta Ontology	2025	[38]
Google Académico	A34	Ontology-driven cybersecurity learning factory: A use case for securing electrical company networks	2024	[39]
Google Académico	A35	OntoMat 4.0: An Ontology Framework for Enhanced Industry 4.0 Maturity Assessment	2025	[40]
Google Académico	A36	Scalable Automation for Iot Cybersecurity Compliance Ontology-Driven Reasoning for Real-Time Assessment	2025	[41]
Google Académico	A37	SoK: Come Together–Unifying Security, Information Theory, and Cognition for a Mixed Reality Deception Attack Ontology & Analysis Framework	2025	[42]
Google Académico	A38	Towards an Ontology of Wargame Design	2025	[43]
Google Académico	A39	Towards an Ontology-Driven Approach for Contextualized Cybersecurity Awareness	2025	[44]
Google Académico	A40	A review: Monitoring situational awareness of smart grid cyber-physical systems and critical asset identification	2023	[45]